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Work Package 2 - Chinese Intellectual Debates and Writings - Deliverable 2.2 – Research Summary of Analysed Sources

During the initial phase of this research project on conceptualising the rule of law in China, a corpus of one hundred research articles from the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) Academic Journals Database was analysed to gain a better understanding of the academic discussion about the concept of the rule of law and its potential variations in China. The author was particularly interested in discussions among Chinese scholars about the content of the term rule of law, whether and how the meaning differs from the "Western" understanding, and the arguments supporting such alterations.

The selection criteria were as follows:

- a) Timeframe: 1979–2022
- b) Language: Written in Chinese by Chinese author(s)
- c) Keywords: 法治 (rule of law) OR 依法治国 (governance according to law)
- d) Fifty most cited articles (based on data from November 30, 2023).

The initial plan was to analyse the thirty most cited articles in total. However, during the collection and close reading process, the author realised that a larger corpus of texts is needed to cover a fuller scope of discussion about the rule of law. Nevertheless, the author acknowledges that the increased number of analysed texts cannot fully encompass the entire spectrum of opinions.

Another clarification point is that older articles might be expected to have more citations due to their extended availability. However, this assumption does not always hold true. For instance, the most cited articles with the keyword "yifazhiguo" predominantly originate from the last decade of the examined period. Furthermore, as mentioned in the subsequent paragraph, the period preceding the actual policy announcement in 2014 is critical for comprehending academic discussions about the rule of law.

The concept of the rule of law began to lose the bourgeois label in the 1990s. Consequently, the CNKI database contains a minimum of relevant articles from the 1980s and early 1990s. However, the author

intends to explore other pertinent sources, including books and book chapters, to bridge this gap. The term "rule of law" appeared repeatedly in official documents in the 1990s. However, it gained prominence after Xi Jinping assumed leadership of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) and State in 2012 and 2013, respectively. This trend is evident in Figures 1 and 2, which depict a significant surge in research articles using keywords like "fazhi" and "yifazhiguo," peaking in 2015 (with 1153 published articles on "fazhi" and 1584 on "yifazhiguo"). This increase correlates with the Fourth Plenary Session of the 18th Central Committee of the Communist Party of China (中国共产党第十八届中央委员会第四次全体会议) held in October 2014. As a result of this event, the Decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Several Major Issues Concerning Comprehensively Promoting the Rule of Law (中共中央关于全面推进依法治国若干重大问题的决定) emphasised the urgency of accelerating the establishment of China as a socialist rule of law country (社会主义法治国家).

Figure 1 Number of published articles with the keyword fazhi

Source: CNKI database, created by the author

Figure 2 Number of published articles with the keyword yifazhiguo

Source: CNKI database, created by the author

Since the peak in 2015, the number of published articles has declined to levels comparable to those before the 2000s. There is a plausible explanation for this trend. The 2014 Central Committee meeting can be seen as the culmination of previous discussions, resulting in policy decisions. Once the policy was established, the room for theoretical exploration of these concepts significantly diminished. Consequently, mainly articles reiterating the Party document and further elaborating on the policy emerged. However, the volume of research publications gradually decreased due to limited space and new inputs. Nevertheless, this decline in academic publications does not necessarily imply that the question of "fazhi" or "yifazhiguo" is no longer relevant.

On the contrary, the actual implementation of policy can be expected to follow the theoretical groundwork phase. We can observe this shift, for instance, in the report published after the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China (中国共产党第十九次全国代表大会). This congress established three stages for building the rule of law in China: a) until 2020, b) from 2020 to 2035, and c) from 2035 to 2049, which coincides with the one-hundredth anniversary of the People's

Republic of China (PRC). However, a more detailed examination of this progression will be conducted in subsequent research.

In this summary, I highlight specific topics from selected articles that I found particularly insightful or thought-provoking. These include interesting arguments, critical assessments, and sometimes even contradictory viewpoints. I also point out recurring themes that appear across multiple articles, suggesting their significance within the research and policy landscape. For clarity, I have organised these findings into three sections – the Party and the government, calls for reforms, and Chinese characteristics – presented in chronological order.

As noted earlier, the concept of "rule of law" has gained widespread popularity since Xi Jinping's rise to power. This trend has led some authors to incorporate the term into their articles primarily to align with the current policy direction. Moreover, many research articles tend to simply reiterate Xi Jinping's speeches and Party documents rather than offering original perspectives. For a complete list of the research articles considered, please refer to DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10123967](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10123967). This document and the list of research articles (D2.1) only serve as a point of departure and source of thoughts for the following deliverables: D2.3 and D2.4.

The Party and the government

The following authors examine the dynamics between the Party and the government in China, specifically the hierarchy of national law and Party regulations. While acknowledging the Party's leadership role, they offer diverse perspectives on the legal hierarchy and how the Party-State relationship shapes China's efforts to build the rule of law.

In the article Reflection on the Construction of Internal Regulations of Communist Party of China, Zhou Yezhong comments that concepts of governing the country according to law, exercising the state power according to law and intra-party democracy are successively institutionalised and put into practice. Therefore, intra-party regulations will play an even more important role. It is necessary to organically combine the construction of intra-party regulations with the construction of the party's governing capacity. According to Zhou, it is essential to apply constitutional thinking, inject factors of the modern rule of law into the construction of intra-party regulations, and firmly establish the concept

of the rule of law within the Party. This will promote the transformation of the Communist Party of China into a more democratic and modern ruling party with the rule of law. (Zhou 2011, p. 47).

In the 2001 article *On Responsible Government and the Role of Supervision in its Realizing Process*, Chen Guoquan states that the relationship between the Party and the government must be reasonably defined to establish a responsible government (Chen 2001, p. 33). The author refers to another scholar, Zhang Guoqin, stating that because the Party occupies a leading position in the national political system, it can lead to the phenomenon of the Party being above the law. He further states that by using Party discipline sanctions instead of national law to pursue administrative responsibility, the government and its staff lose their legal responsibility for the Constitution, civil law, criminal law, and administrative law. Therefore, it is necessary to establish an administrative responsibility system in China to ensure the political leadership of the Communist Party of China (Zhang 1990, quoted in Chen 2001, p. 33).

In the 2012 article *Re-discussing the Rule of Law, Legal Thinking and Legal Means* by Jiang Mingan, the author concludes that the socialist rule of law includes five aspects, namely, governing the country according to law, law enforcement, fairness and justice, serving the overall situation, and the Party leadership. These five aspects complement each other and embody the organic unity of Party leadership, people's participation, and law-based governance (Jiang 2012, p. 80).

According to Chen Jinzhao's article *Interpretation of "Legal Thinking and Legal Approach"*, the actual dependence of the rule of law on political power is the great enemy of the rule of law (Chen 2013, p. 92). The political ideology centred on the maintenance of power has many adverse effects on the construction of the rule of law (Ibid., p. 96). Chen further states that although the rule of law should adapt to those national conditions and characteristics that truly express the feelings of the Chinese people, we must not let people use this as an excuse to hinder the progress of the rule of law (Ibid., pp. 92–93).

In a 2013 article *Basic Theoretical Issues Concerning the CCP Regulations and Rules*, Wang Zhemin discusses how to deal with the relationship between intra-party regulations and national laws. Wang believes that China has promoted institutionalisation and standardisation on two fronts since the reform and opening up. One is the construction of the country's rule of law. The other front is the standardisation and institutionalisation of the party, which has initially formed a framework of intra-party laws and regulations. These two sets of norms are equally crucial to the long-term peace and

stability of the country, and both are indispensable. Therefore, national law and the Party's policy are two sides of the same coin and are mutually reinforcing. According to Wang, the Party's policy is the soul of the law, and the law is the embodiment and legalisation of the Party's policy. To govern according to national laws is to govern according to the Party's policies. In the situation of governing the country according to law, the law has become the primary, irreplaceable and essential carrier and guarantee for carrying the Party's policies, implementing the Party's policies, and ensuring the implementation of the Party's lines, principles, and policies (Wang 2013, p. 146).

According to Chu Hongqi and Jia Ji'e's article Educational Governance and Educational Good Governance, the rule of law is a fundamental requirement for effective governance. Any governance activity and subject must act as the law prescribes. The rule of law opposes the rule of man as it not only regulates the behaviour of citizens but also restricts the behaviour of the government (Chu, Jia 2014, p. 9).

In their 2014 article On Innovation of Social Governance, Jiang Bixin and Li Mo argue that building legal thinking requires establishing the authority of the rule of law. This requires leaders and public officials at all levels to firmly establish the awareness of the supremacy of the Constitution and the authority of the law. To achieve this, the bottom line of the law must not be broken for the sake of maintaining stability, illegal demands of individuals must not be accommodated for fear of petitioning, and furthermore, we must not prioritise individual justice over the universal justice guaranteed by the rule of law. (Jiang, Li 2014, p. 30).

According to Li Lin's article Ruling the Country by Law and Promoting the Modernization of State Governance, the CCP operates within the bounds of the Constitution and laws. It demonstrates leadership by adhering to the law, promoting impartiality, and serving as a role model. (Li 2014, p. 12).

In the article The Legal System of Political Party in the Process of State Governance of Law, Tian Feilong argues that Party members hold the distinction of being "advanced citizens." This distinction comes with unique responsibilities, including actively promoting the legal system's progress, participating in experimentation with new systems, and serving the people. (Tian 2015, p. 91).

In the article Rule of Law: Good Law and Good Governance, Wang Liming argues that good law and good governance will lead China to become a country under the rule of law (Wang 2015, p. 120). The author believes that good laws should reflect the will and interests of the vast majority of the people, uphold fairness and justice, safeguard individual fundamental rights, and reflect the natural course of

social development. Lawmaking should prioritise the people, reflecting both the objective laws of societal progress and the sentiments of the nation and its citizens (Ibid., p. 115).

In his 2015 article, Jiang Shigong discusses the construction of a "party-based rule of law" that aligns with China's reality and differs from the "Western" concepts of the rule of law. To construct the "party rule of law", the core is to properly handle the relationship between the Party Constitution and the Constitution, Party regulations and national laws, and policies and laws (Jiang 2015, p. 18). Jiang argues that even though the National People's Congress is the highest authority, it does not have the power to change major policies formulated by the Party Central Committee through legislation or amendments to laws. Therefore, regarding the constitutional system, the Party Central Committee is higher than the National People's Congress (Ibid., p. 21).

In their article *On the Relationship between the Party Regulations and the State Law*, Ji Yaping and Zhi Hanzhen express a viewpoint that differs from that of Qian Shigong (2015). They maintain that the supremacy of state law must be the fundamental principle guiding the relationship between party regulations and state law. This implies that while intra-party regulations may be stringent, they must never violate the 'red line' of state law supremacy (Ji, Zhi 2018, p. 36).

Zhang Wenxian, a prominent Chinese legal scholar and jurist, authored the second most cited article, *The Rule of Law and Modernization of National Governance*. His work's significant presence in the corpus (appearing ten times) highlights his influence on China's legal thought and potential impact on legislation. Published two months before the 18th Central Committee meeting, this article emphasises a core principle of the Socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics: upholding the Communist Party of China's leadership as the fundamental guarantee for both people's democracy and the rule of law. Zhang argues that strengthening the Party and its leadership is necessary to ensure it serves as the ultimate guarantor of the rule of law (Zhang 2014, p. 26). This position is widely echoed in articles following the 2014 Central Committee meeting. Crucially, as the rule of law is a hallmark of a modern, well-governed nation, legislative improvements must be coupled with effective implementation.

In his 2015 article *The Cultural Connotation of Rule of Law: The Cultural Construction of China's Rule of Law*, Zhang Wenxian acknowledges that Western culture and values hold some merit, specifically citing Marxism as a value system originating in the West with global influence. He emphasises that while values may have universal appeal, political systems, as carriers of these values, cannot be universal (Zhang 2015, p. 22). He also references President Xi Jinping's statement at the 60th

Anniversary Commemorative Meeting of the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence, highlighting the call for jointly promoting the rule of law in international relations (Ibid., p. 23).

In the article *Research on Xi Jinping's Thought on the Rule of Law (Part 1) — The Distinctive Characteristics of Xi Jinping's Thought on the Rule of Law*, Zhang Wenxian highlights Xi Jinping's emphasis on studying China's legal history. While open to learning from other systems, Xi stresses the importance of avoiding "total Westernization" and preserving China's unique approach. He advocates for China to shape the international rule of law and contribute to a global order that supports the nation's goals (Ibid., p. 13). Xi views the Party's leadership and socialist rule of law as mutually reinforcing, stating that each is essential to the success of the other (Ibid., p. 17).

Wang Ruolei, in his 2016 article, asserts that the basic concept that "the Party must abide by the law" cannot be shaken. He emphasises that the essence of the rule of law lies in universal adherence, and political parties – even those serving as the central nervous system of the political structure – are no exception (Wang 2016, p. 22). He further comments that the key to the success or failure of China's rule of law lies in whether the ruling party abides by the law (Ibid.). To achieve this, he calls for enhancing the legal framework surrounding the Party's governance. It would entail embedding the rule of law into intra-party regulations, ensuring open, transparent, and stable party rules that limit discretionary power (Ibid., p. 25). Furthermore, Wang stresses the dangers of unwritten rules within the Party, which are incompatible with the spirit of modern rule of law. He argues that individuals can foresee consequences only with clear, transparent regulations and act accordingly, a principle that must extend equally to intra-party regulations (Ibid., pp. 25–26).

Zhang Wenxian, in his 2017 article, argues that China should actively participate in and strive to lead international legislation, participate in and support global law enforcement, international justice, and international arbitration, participate in international legal services, and actively carry out legal diplomacy (Zhang 2017, p. 17).

According to Jiang Mingan, there is no doubt that the Party's rules are under national law and that any provisions made by the Party's internal regulations must not conflict with the Constitution and laws (Jiang 2017, p. 75). He also argues that specific Party rules apply within and outside the Party because the CCP is not an ordinary political party or ruling party. It is a ruling party that leads all national affairs. Therefore, it not only uses party rules to regulate intra-party affairs but also sometimes to adjust national affairs at the same time (Ibid., p. 76). Jiang argues that to establish the rule of law in China,

the CCP must prioritise its own transformation into a ruling party governed by the rule of law. He asserts that without the ruling party's adherence to the rule of law, a nationwide system of legal governance is impossible (Ibid., p. 78). To facilitate this transformation, Jiang proposes urgently needed improvements to the CCP's internal regulatory system, focusing on four key areas: 1) Inner-party democratic system, e.g. decision-making democracy, selection and appointment of people, and electoral democracy; 2) Party affairs disclosure system, 3) Declaration, verification and disclosure system for leading cadres' family property and other personal matters; and 4) Inner-party supervision system (Ibid., p. 78).

In his 2017 article *The Construction of the Intra-Party Legal System from the Perspective of the Rule of Law*, Wang Jianqin criticises the ambiguity between party regulations and state law. He posits that the scope of Party affairs can be divided into internal matters and external affairs, the latter primarily concerning national and social issues related to politics, economics, and public welfare. Wang notes that 14% of the Party's internal regulations involve external affairs, often issued jointly with state organs. This practice of joint publications, according to Wang, creates two problems: first, the nature and status of such documents are unclear, and second, there's an overlap of authority between party regulations and state laws, blurring their boundaries and exacerbating confusion within the legal system (Wang 2017, p. 38).

Calls for reforms

Scholarship from the 1990s and early 2000s reflects a critical stance towards China's judicial and administrative systems, with calls for reform of both the legal system and the Party. While some of these desired reforms have been implemented, it remains uncertain whether the scholars cited below would approve of the outcomes of these changes.

In the 1999 article titled *On Governing the Country according to Law*, the authors state that when improving a fair judicial system, it is necessary to pay attention to the following points: judicial organs independently exercise judicial and procuratorial powers in accordance with the law, and no administrative agencies, social groups or individuals are allowed to interfere (Wang et al. 1999, p. 6). They add that no matter how high their current position is or how extraordinary their past achievements are, ordinary citizens and leading cadres have no privileges above or beyond the law (Ibid., p. 8). They believe the Party must act within the Constitution's and the law's scope. The Party

leads the people to formulate the Constitution and laws, and the Party must also lead the people to abide by the Constitution and laws (Ibid., p. 9).

In the 2002 article *Theoretical Reflections on the Pending Detention System*, Chen Ruihua calls for judicial reform while focusing on pretrial detention in China. The author argues that strengthening the public security organs and police power and depriving citizens of their freedom are obstacles to moving China towards the rule of law (Chen 2002, p. 81).

In his 2003 article *Legal Thinking and Its Significance to the Rule of Law*, Chen Jinzhao critically assesses China's underdeveloped research on legal thinking methods. He identifies these methods as a fundamental prerequisite for realising the rule of law. Despite this initial shortcoming, Chen observes positive changes over the previous decade, highlighting advancements in the construction of legal systems. He argues that these shifts in legal thinking are crucial, promoting more profound research and enhancing the public's legal understanding. Ultimately, Chen asserts that this evolution in understanding will reshape society's perception of the law and facilitate a transition towards the rule of law (Chen 2003, p. 69).

In their 2003 article *On the Right to Know*, Wang Xigen and Chen Yanguang assert that China, as a signatory of the International Covenant on Human Rights, has a duty to uphold its provisions. They emphasise the urgent need to enshrine the right to know into domestic law, fulfilling China's commitment to the Covenant and transforming its principles into actionable legislation (Wang, Chen 2003, p. 74).

The most cited article in the corpus, *Legality¹, Financial Development and Economic Growth under Financial Repression*, by Lu Feng and Yao Yang, focuses on China's economy and explores the potential negative impact of the rule of law on financial development. Notably, the authors don't explore the specific definition of the rule of law used in their analysis. Instead, they measure its implementation solely through the annual rate of economic cases concluded by provincial courts. They argue that reforming the banking system and liberalising interest rates are more critical for China's financial development than prioritising improvements in the rule of law (Lu, Yang 2004).

In their 2005 article *On Public Credibility of the Judiciary*, Zheng Chengliang and Zhang Yingxia argue that two key factors hinder the public's trust in the judiciary: 1) Low quality of judicial personnel – the

¹ the Chinese term 法治 is translated as legality in the English title in the CNKI database

authors point out that the qualifications and competence of personnel within the judicial system fall short of expectations, and 2) Lagging judicial system: the authors argue that the judicial system itself fails to keep pace with the advancements of society (Zheng, Zhang 2005, p. 9).

In his 2006 article *The Wave of Petitions and the Path Selection of China's Dispute Resolution Mechanism*, Zhou Yongkun argues against strengthening China's petition system. He believes this would shift the dispute resolution mechanism towards an arbitrary rule of man rather than a robust rule of law. Zhou advocates for prioritising the strengthening of the court system (Zhou 2006, p. 47).

In their 2006 article *Some Thoughts on Improving My Country's Administrative Accountability System*, authors Ding Xiancun and Xia Shumei advocate for an improved administrative accountability system. They argue that it should be integrated within the rule of law framework, emphasising the importance of due process to ensure the system's legitimacy, regularity, and the equal application of responsibilities (Ding, Xia 2006, p. 17).

In the article *On the Governance of the Administrative Discretion*, Zhou Youyong offers a critical assessment of China's limited judicial review process. He advocates for strengthening legislative control over administrative discretion to address its widespread abuse. Zhou highlights the public perception that the legislature has failed to regulate administrative power adequately, leading to the current situation (Zhou 2007, p. 123). While acknowledging China's unique circumstances, he emphasises the importance of learning from developed nations with established rule-of-law systems (Ibid.).

In his 2008 article *The Tension between Governance and State-building*, Yu Jianxing argues that a sound judicial and law enforcement system serves as a crucial platform for establishing or reconstructing a nation. This system, characterised by legal, procedural, and institutional frameworks, facilitates negotiation and reflection among various stakeholders, including individuals, organisations, governments, and society as a whole (Yu 2008, p. 93).

Chinese characteristics

The phrase "Chinese characteristics" is ubiquitous in Chinese discourse, implying a unique approach without a precise definition. It often signals that established concepts – like democracy, human rights, or the rule of law – carry distinct meanings within the Chinese context. However, this interpretation

remains a point of contention, with interpretations of the phrase and its implications varying across different viewpoints.

In his 2001 article *Civil Society and Political State: The Foundation and Limits of the Rule of Law*, Ma Changshan acknowledges that cultural traditions, history, and other factors play a role in shaping the rule of law. However, he emphasises that the fundamental factor lies in the state's and society's dynamic. Consequently, he suggests limiting the focus on "local resources" in discussions about the rule of law (Ma 2001, pp. 40–41).

In the article *On the Exercise of State Power by the Communist Party of China in accordance with the Law*, Shi Taifeng and Zhang Hengshan posit that the Western rule of law is intrinsically linked with multi-party systems and separation of powers. They assert that, as a socialist state, China has a fundamentally distinct approach to implementing the rule of law. China cannot and should not adopt Western models and instead must prioritise the leadership of the Communist Party. The authors define this leadership as the essential distinction between socialist and capitalist rule of law. To them, governance in accordance with the law strengthens the Party's role in guiding the nation. (Shi, Zhang 2003, p. 19).

In their 2004 article, Guo Xinhua and Wang Ping highlight the tension between China's modernising legal system and its deep-rooted traditional customs in rural areas. Despite the growing influence of the law, people often resort to traditional social controls, sometimes circumventing or adapting official legal practices (Guo, Wang 2004, p. 71). The authors advocate for a legal framework that acknowledges China's unique context, respecting the public's behavioural patterns shaped by traditional culture. They believe laws can be effectively implemented only by aligning with these cultural values, fostering a genuinely robust rule of law with strong ties to local practices (Ibid., p. 76).

In the 2009 article *On the Road to Chinese Characteristic Socialist Rule of Law*, Zhang Wenxian contends that Western rule of law models are not universal and should not be blindly adopted by China. He emphasises the crucial role of the Communist Party in upholding people's democracy and implementing the rule of law to ensure that the people are the masters of the country. The author believes the fundamental principles of the Chinese socialist rule of law are inseparable from Party leadership (Zhang 2009, p. 11). Zhang outlines the historical development of China's unique rule-of-law system, shaped by the struggles against "feudalism," "ultra-leftism," and "Westernization." He defines its essential characteristics: 1) upholding Party leadership while prioritising people's

democracy and governance in accordance with the law, 2) integrating law-based governance with the exercise of state power according to the law, 3) balancing law-based governance with governance based on virtue, 4) building a society under the rule of law that aligns with China's specific context, and 5) preserving Chinese legal traditions while learning from global legal advancements (Ibid., pp. 13–14).

In their article *On the Human Welfare Law*, Fu Zitang and Chang An advocate for a balanced approach to international human rights conventions. While acknowledging their importance, they stress the need to adapt these principles to China's unique context and prioritise the needs of its large rural population. They argue that the most crucial human rights issue in China centres on the well-being of farmers (Fu, Chang 2009, p. 33).

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